

Thursday, March 24, 2016 5:20:19 AM

#	Query	Limiters/Expanders	Last Run Via	Results
S4	S1 AND S2 AND S3	Search modes - Find all my search terms	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL with Full Text	190
S3	((MH "Exercise") OR (MH "Therapeutic Exercise") OR (MH "Balance Training, Physical") OR ((MH "Balance, Postural") AND (therap* or training* OR exercise*))) OR (TX (exercise OR physical N3 therapy OR physiotherapy OR pilates OR (((muscle N3 strength) OR resistance OR balance) N3 (training OR therapy))))	Search modes - Find all my search terms	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL with Full Text	307,481
S2	TI (((motor N3 control) OR (neuromuscular N3 control) OR (motor N3 skill) OR (cognit* N3 motor) OR (cognitive N3 trunk) OR feedback OR (swiss N3 ball)) N6 (training OR exercise* OR therapy OR rehabilitation OR mov*)) OR TI ((cognit* OR propriocept* OR coordinative OR voluntary OR deliberat* OR intentional* OR willful OR wilful OR purpose* OR designed OR planned OR intended) N6 (training	Search modes - Find all my search terms	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL with Full Text	19,891

OR exercise* OR therapy OR
 rehabilitation OR mov*)) OR T1
 (sensorimotor OR sensorymotor OR
 (sensory N3 motor) OR videogames
 OR exergames OR "dual task" OR
 proprioception OR (coordinat* N3
 muscle*)) OR AB (((motor N3 control)
 OR (neuromuscular N3 control) OR
 (motor N3 skill) OR (cognit* N3
 motor) OR (cognitive N3 trunk) OR
 feedback OR (swiss N3 ball)) N6
 (training OR exercise* OR therapy OR
 rehabilitation OR mov*)) OR AB
 ((cognit* OR propriocept* OR
 coordinative OR voluntary OR
 deliberat* OR intentional* OR willful
 OR wilful OR purpose* OR designed
 OR planned OR intended) N6 (training
 OR exercise* OR therapy OR
 rehabilitation OR mov*)) OR AB
 (sensorimotor OR sensorymotor OR
 (sensory N3 motor) OR videogames
 OR exergames OR "dual task" OR
 proprioception OR (coordinat* N3
 muscle*))

S1

(((MH "Torso") OR (MH "Thorax+")
 OR (MH "Pelvis") OR (MH "Back")
 OR (MH "Abdomen+") OR TX (torso
 OR trunk OR back OR abdomen OR
 pelvis OR thorax)) AND TX (muscle
 N3 strength OR ((muscle N3
 composition) AND (balance OR

Search modes - Find all my search
 terms

Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases 3,007
 Search Screen - Advanced Search
 Database - CINAHL with Full Text

“functional performance” OR (falls
AND (association OR relationship OR
correlation)))) OR TX (trunk OR core
OR postural) N3 (strenght* OR
stabil*) AND ((MH "Aged+") OR TX
((aged OR elder*) N3 (person* OR
patient* OR man OR men OR woman
OR women OR people)))